

Global Type Inference for Java using ASP

Andreas Stadelmeier¹, Martin Plümicke¹

¹Duale Hochschule Baden-Württemberg, Stuttgart, Germany

Abstract

Global type inference for Java is able to compute correct types for an input program which has no type annotations at all, but turns out to be NP-hard. Former implementations of the algorithm therefore struggled with bad runtime performance. In this [original paper](#) we translate the type inference algorithm for Featherweight Generic Java to an Answer Set Program. Answer Set Programming (ASP) promises to solve complex computational search problems as long as they are finite domain. This paper shows that it is possible to implement global type inference for Featherweight Generic Java (FGJ) as an ASP program. Afterwards we compared the ASP implementation with our own implementation in Java exposing promising results. Another advantage is that the specification of the algorithm can be translated one on one to ASP code leading to less errors in the respective implementation.

Keywords

type inference, java, programming languages, answer set programming

1. Global Type Inference

Java is a strictly typed programming language. The current versions come with a local type inference feature that allows the programmer to omit type annotations in some places like argument types of lambda expressions for example. But methods still have to be fully typed including argument and return types. We work at a global type inference algorithm for Java which is able to compute correct types for a Java program with no type annotations at all.

A possible input for our algorithm is shown in figure 1. Here the method `untypedMethod` is missing its argument type for `var` and its return type. Global type inference works in two steps. First we generate a set of subtype constraints, which are later unified resulting in a type solution consisting of type unifiers σ . Every missing type is replaced by a type placeholder. In this example the type placeholder `var` is a placeholder for the type of the `var` variable. The `ret` placeholder represents the return type of the `untypedMethod` method. Also shown as a comment behind the respective method call. There are two types of type constraints. A subtype constraint like $var \leq C1$ meaning that the unification algorithm has to find a type replacement for `var` which is a subtype of `C1`. Due to the Java type system being reflexive one possible solution would be $\sigma(var) = C1$. A constraint $var \doteq C1$ directly results in $\sigma(ret) = C1$.

Our type inference algorithms for Java are described in a formal manner in [1],[2]. The first prototype implementation put the focus on a correct implementation rather than fast execution times. Depending on the input it currently takes upto several minutes or even days to compute

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```

class C1 {
    C1 self(){
        return this;
    }
}
class C2 {
    C2 self(){
        return this;
    }
}
class Example {
    untypedMethod(var) {
        return var.self(); //  $\implies \{var \prec C1, ret \doteq C1\} \parallel \{var \prec C2, ret \doteq C2\}$ 
    }
}

```

Figure 1: Java program where a method is missing type annotations

all or even one possible type solution. To make them usable in practice we now focus on decreasing the runtime to a feasible level.

2. Motivation

The nature of the global type inference algorithm causes the search space of the unification algorithm to increase exponentially with every ambiguous method call. Java allows overloaded methods causing our type inference algorithm to create so called Or-Constraints. This happens if multiple classes implement a method with the same name and the same amount of parameters. Given the input program in figure 1 we do not know, which method `self` is meant for the method call `var.self()`, because there is no type annotation for `var`.

An Or-Constraint like $\{var \prec C1, ret \doteq C1\} \parallel \{var \prec C2, ret \doteq C2\}$ means that either the the constraint set $\{var \prec C1, ret \doteq C1\}$ or $\{var \prec C2, ret \doteq C2\}$ has to be satisfied. If we set the type of `var` to `C1`, then the return type of the method will be `C1` as well. If we set it to `C2` then also the return type will be `C2`. There are two possibilities therefore the Or-Constraint.

If we chain multiple overloaded method calls together we end up with multiple Or-Constraints. The type unification algorithm **Unify** only sees the supplied constraints and has to potentially try all combinations of them. This is proven in [2] and is the reason why type inference for Featherweight Generic Java is NP-hard. Let's have a look at the following alternation of our example:

```

    untypedMethod(var) {
        return var.self().self().self().self();
    }

```

Figure 2: Java program with stacked ambiguous method calls

Now there are four chained method calls leading to four Or-Constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{var < C1, r1 \doteq C1\} \parallel \{var < C2, r1 \doteq C2\} \\ & \{r1 < C1, r2 \doteq C1\} \parallel \{r1 < C2, r2 \doteq C2\} \\ & \{r2 < C1, r3 \doteq C1\} \parallel \{r2 < C2, r3 \doteq C2\} \\ & \{r3 < C1, ret \doteq C1\} \parallel \{r3 < C2, ret \doteq C2\} \end{aligned}$$

The placeholder $r1$ stands for the return type of the first call to `self` and $r2$ for the return type of the second call and so on. It is obvious that this constraint set only has two solutions. The variable `var` and the return type of the method as well as all intermediate placeholders $r1 - r3$ get either the type `C1` or `C2`. A first prototype implementation of the **Unify** algorithm [3] simply created the cartesian product of all Or-Constraints, 16 possibilities in this example, and iteratively tried all of them. This leads to an exponential runtime increase with every added overloaded method call. Even though the current algorithm is equipped with various optimizations as presented in [4] and [5] there are still runtime issues when dealing with many Or-Constraints.

Our global type inference algorithm should construct type solutions in real time. Then it can effectively be used as a Java compiler which can deal with large inputs of untyped Java code. Another use case scenario is as an editor plugin which helps a Java programmer by enabling him to write untyped Java code and letting our tool insert the missing type statements. For both applications a short execution time is vital.

Answer Set programming promises to solve complex search problems in a highly optimized way. The idea in this paper is to implement the algorithm presented in [2] as an ASP program and see how well it handles our type unification problem.

3. Type unification

The global type inference algorithm works in two steps. First a set of subtype constraints is generated which are unified resulting in a type solution consisting of type unifiers σ . Java type unification is considered in different contributions. In [6] the basic ideas are presented and a first approach of the algorithm is given. The algorithm is the type unification algorithm for global type inference of GJ [7]. The type parameters of GJ had been invariant and without wildcards. In [1] the type system is extended by wildcards and in [8, 3] the first implementation is described. In this approach the type system is restricted in a way, such that bounds of type parameters are either `Object` or another type parameter. In [2], finally, the type unification algorithm of [6] is extended such that any bound can be determined for type parameters.

In the following we present the algorithm in a form which is used in [6] and [1].

The type unification has as input a set of subtype constraints. The result is a set of pairs of constraints consisting only of type variables and a substitution which solves the input subtype constraints.

First the conjunctions of or-constraints are transformed to a set of constraint sets in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned}
& cs \wedge \dots \wedge cs \wedge \left(\begin{array}{c} [cs \wedge \dots \wedge cs] \\ || \dots \\ || [cs \wedge \dots \wedge cs] \end{array} \right) \wedge \dots \wedge \left(\begin{array}{c} [cs \wedge \dots \wedge cs] \\ || \dots \\ || [cs \wedge \dots \wedge cs] \end{array} \right) \\
& \Rightarrow \{ \{ cs, \dots, cs, [cs, \dots, cs], \dots, [cs, \dots, cs] \} \\
& \quad \dots \\
& \quad \{ cs, \dots, cs, [cs, \dots, cs], \dots, [cs, \dots, cs] \} \}
\end{aligned}$$

For each set of constraints algorithm is started:

1. **Reduce:** Each constraint of the form $\theta < \theta'$ and $\theta \doteq \theta'$, where θ and θ' are no type variables, are reduced to constraints of the form: $A < \phi$, $\phi < A$, $A \doteq \phi$. where A and B are type variables and ϕ is an arbitrary type term. The reduce rules of the type system without wildcards is a subset of the reduce rules of the type system with wildcards.
2. **Failure** If after application of the reduce rules there constraints of other forms, as $\theta < \theta'$ or $\theta \doteq \theta'$, where θ and θ' are no type variables the algorithm **fails**.
3. **Smaller and greater:** The constraints of the form $A < \theta$ and $\theta < A$ where θ is no type variable are resolved by determination of all sub- and all super-types, respectively.
4. **Cartesian product and fork:** The type unification algorithm is continued for all elements of the cartesian product of the solutions of Step 3 in a forked thread, separately.

Finally, the results of the forked threads are united and returned as result of the algorithm.

5. **Substitution:** In the respective thread for all $A \doteq \theta$ the type variable A is substituted in all constraints by θ .
6. **Results and recursion** For the termination we need a definition for a solved form.

Definition 1 (Solved form). A set of constraints $cons = \{(T_1 \doteq \theta_1), \dots, (T_n \doteq \theta_n), (T'_1 < T''_1), \dots, (T'_m < T''_m)\}$ is in *solved form*, if T_1, \dots, T_n are pairwise different type variables, $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n$ are types, for all $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ holds: T_i does not occur in θ_j , for $k \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ T'_k and T''_k are type variables, and for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ holds $T_i \notin \{T'_1, T''_1, \dots, T'_m, T''_m\}$.

If the set of constraints is in solved form, the algorithm thread terminates with the pair of type variable constraints $\{(T'_1 < T''_1), \dots, (T'_m < T''_m)\}$ and the substitutions $\{T_i \mapsto \theta_i \mid (T_i \doteq \theta_i) \in cons\}$.

Otherwise the algorithm thread is called recursively with the set of constraints.

We present an example for the type unification.

Example Let the classes OL and OLMain be given.

```

class OL      {
    Integer m(Integer x) { return x + x; }
    Double m(Double x) { return x + x; }
    String m(String x) { return x + x; }
    Boolean m(Boolean x) { return x || x; }
}

class OLMain1 {
    H main(I x)({
        J ol;
        ol:J = new OL();
        return (ol:J.m(x:I)):K;
    }):K}

```

The input for the type unification algorithm is given as:

$$(\text{OL} \triangleleft J) \wedge \left(\begin{array}{l} [(J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \triangleleft \text{String}), (K \doteq \text{String})] \\ || [(J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \triangleleft \text{Boolean}), (K \doteq \text{Boolean})] \\ || [(J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \triangleleft \text{Integer}), (K \doteq \text{Integer})] \\ || [(J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \triangleleft \text{Double}), (K \doteq \text{Double})] \end{array} \right) \wedge (K \triangleleft H)$$

The given or-constraints are distributed:

$$\{ \{ (\text{OL} \triangleleft J), (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \triangleleft \text{String}), (K \doteq \text{String}), (K \triangleleft H) \} \\
\{ (\text{OL} \triangleleft J), (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \triangleleft \text{Boolean}), (K \doteq \text{Boolean}), (K \triangleleft H) \} \\
\{ (\text{OL} \triangleleft J), (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \triangleleft \text{Integer}), (K \doteq \text{Integer}), (K \triangleleft H) \} \\
\{ (\text{OL} \triangleleft J), (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \triangleleft \text{Double}), (K \doteq \text{Double}), (K \triangleleft H) \} \}$$

For each set of constraints the algorithm is called.

1. **Reduce:** Nothing is reduced in any set of constraints.
2. **Failure:** All sets of constraints do not fail.
3. **Smaller and greater:** In this step ($J \doteq \text{OL}$) in any case and ($I \doteq \text{String}$), ($I \doteq \text{Boolean}$), ($I \doteq \text{Integer}$), and ($I \doteq \text{Double}$), respectively, are determined.
4. **Cartesian product and fork:** In no case a cartesian is built.
5. **Substution:** K is substituted in ($K \triangleleft H$), respectively: ($\text{String} \triangleleft H$), ($\text{Boolean} \triangleleft H$), ($\text{Integer} \triangleleft H$), and ($\text{Double} \triangleleft H$).
6. **Results and recursion:** As no set of constraints is in solved form for all constraint sets the algorithm is called recursively.

In Step 1 and 2 nothing is changed:

3. Smaller and greater:

For all constraint sets the constraints ($\text{String} \triangleleft H$), ($\text{Boolean} \triangleleft H$), ($\text{Integer} \triangleleft H$), and ($\text{Double} \triangleleft H$) are solved. For all constraints the **greater** function has to be determined.

```

greater(String) = {String, Object, java.io.Serializable, CharSequence,
                  Comparable<String>, Comparable<? extends String>}

```

¹In OLMain the type placeholder are noted which are solved by the type unification algorithm.

greater(Boolean) = { Boolean, Object, java.io.Serializable, Comparable<Boolean>, Comparable<? extends Boolean> }

greater(Integer) = { Integer, Number, Object, java.io.Serializable, Comparable<Integer>, Comparable<? extends Integer> }

greater(Double) = { Double, Number, Object, java.io.Serializable, Comparable<Double>, Comparable<? extends Double> }

4. Cartesian product and fork:

The step the cartesian products are built, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{ \{ (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \doteq \text{String}), (K \doteq \text{String}), (H \doteq \text{String}) \}, \\ & \{ (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \doteq \text{String}), (K \doteq \text{String}), (H \doteq \text{Object}) \}, \\ & \{ (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \doteq \text{String}), (K \doteq \text{String}), (H \doteq \text{java.io.Serializable}) \}, \\ & \{ (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \doteq \text{String}), (K \doteq \text{String}), (H \doteq \text{CharSequence}) \}, \\ & \{ (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \doteq \text{String}), (K \doteq \text{String}), (H \doteq \text{Comparable<String>}) \}, \\ & \{ (J \doteq \text{OL}), (I \doteq \text{String}), (K \doteq \text{String}), (H \doteq \text{Comparable<? extends String>}) \} \end{aligned}$$

For Boolean, Integer, and Double the cartesian product are built analogously.

5. Substition: As all constraint sets are in solved form no substitution is done.

6. Results and recursion: The algorithm terminates with the corresponding substitutions. The set of type variable constraints is empty.

4. ASP Implementation

Our ASP Implementation implements the algorithm of [2] which means that Featherweight Generic Java is our base and the type system has invariant generics, no wildcards, and no F-bound type parameters. The implementation replaces the unification step of the type inference algorithm. So the input is a set of constraints c and the output is a set of unifiers σ .

Answer Set Programming has a declarative way of formulating search problems. In ASP you encode the problem as a set of logical rules and facts and let an ASP solver (like `clingo`²) compute one or more stable models (also called answer sets). A *stable model* is a self-justifying, minimal³, and internally consistent interpretation of the program [9].

Translated to our algorithm this means that the input set of constraints C are the facts and the implication rules shown in figure 5 are the logic rules. Thus, a stable model then must be a constraint set that satisfies all the rules, contains the input set of constraints, and is minimal (see definition 2). Furthermore, the rules of our algorithm Ω are formulated in a way that each input set of constraints C either ends in a *fail* condition -meaning there is no possible solution- or leads to a stable model C_S that contains correct unifiers of the form $\sigma(a) = G$ for every type placeholder a in the input constraints. We prove those statements in chapter 5.

²<https://potassco.org/clingo/>

³all rules are satisfied and no proper subset of it satisfies the same conditions

c	::=	$T < T \mid T \doteq T$	Constraint
T, S	::=	$a \mid N$	Type placeholder or Type
N	::=	$C < \bar{P} >$	Class Type containing type placeholders
G	::=	$C < \bar{G} >$	Class Type not containing type placeholders
P	::=	$a \mid G$	Well-Formed Parameter

Figure 3: Syntax of types and constraints

G are types that contain no type placeholders. A type P is either a type placeholder or a type not containing type placeholders at all. The reason for those definitions is that they restrict type placeholder to only appear in the uppermost level of a type parameter list.

Definition 2. *Stable Model* A stable model (or answer set) of an input set C is a set of constraints C_S with $C \subseteq C_S$ that:

- Satisfies all the rules
- Is complete: If the premise of any rule in Ω is satisfied by elements of C_S , then the conclusion of that rule must also be included in C_S .
- Is minimal (no unnecessary atoms)

All extends relations in the input program have to satisfy the WF-Class rule. This restriction is necessary because our algorithm only supports type placeholders in the uppermost layer of a type parameter list. WF-Class rule ensures that supertypes generated by the Super rule are well-formed. For example the class definition `class Matrix<A> extends List<List<A>>` is not supported by our algorithm Ω . If an input C contains a constraint `Matrix<a> < b` then the Super rule would require for a `b \doteq List<List<a>>` constraint where the type `List<List<a>>` is **not well-formed** according to the rules in figure 4 and therefore not supported by our algorithm.

WF-CONSTRAINTS $\frac{\bar{S}_1, \bar{S}_2, \bar{T}_1, \bar{T}_2 \text{ ok} \quad C = \{\bar{S}_1 \doteq \bar{S}_2, \bar{T}_1 < \bar{T}_2\}}{C \text{ ok}}$	WF-TYPE $C < \bar{P} > \text{ ok}$	WF-VAR $a \text{ ok}$
WF-CLASS $\frac{\text{for any } \bar{a} : ([\bar{X}/\bar{a}]N) \text{ ok}}{\text{class } C < \bar{X} > < N \text{ ok}}$		

Figure 4: Well-formedness condition

4.1. Unification Algorithm

All the implication rules depicted in this chapter can be translated to ASP statements as described in chapter 6. The whole algorithm is depicted in figure 5

The last rules in figure 5 are needed for lemma 5. Without them there would be no guarantee that every type placeholder ends up in a constraint of the form $a \doteq G$ (see lemma 5). The

Subtyping:			
S-REFL $T <: T$	S-TRANS $\frac{T_1 <: T_2 \quad T_2 <: T_3}{T_1 <: T_3}$	S-CLASS $\frac{\text{class } C < \bar{X} > < N}{C < \bar{T} > <: [\bar{T}/\bar{X}]N}$	
Unify:			
SUBST-L $\frac{a \doteq T_1 \quad a <: T_2}{T_1 <: T_2}$	SUBST-R $\frac{a \doteq T_1 \quad T_2 <: a}{T_2 <: T_1}$	SUBST-EQUAL $\frac{a \doteq T_1 \quad a \doteq T_2}{T_1 \doteq T_2}$	SWAP $\frac{T_1 \doteq T_2}{T_2 \doteq T_1}$
SUBST-PARAM $\frac{a \doteq G \quad T \doteq C < P_1, \dots, a, \dots, P_n >}{T \doteq C < P_1, \dots, G, \dots, P_n >}$	SUBST-PARAM-RIGHT $\frac{a \doteq G \quad b <: C < T_1, \dots, a, \dots, T_n >}{b <: C < P_1, \dots, G, \dots, P_n >}$		
SUBST-PARAM-LEFT $\frac{a \doteq G \quad C < P_1, \dots, a, \dots, P_n > <: b}{C < P_1, \dots, G, \dots, P_n > <: b}$	S-OBJECT $a <: \text{Object}$	ADAPT $\frac{N <: C < P_1, \dots, P_n > \quad N <: C < P'_1, \dots, P'_n >}{P_1 \doteq P'_1 \dots P_n \doteq P'_n}$	
REDUCE $\frac{C < P_1, \dots, P_n > \doteq C < P'_1, \dots, P'_n >}{P_i \doteq P'_i}$	SUPER $\frac{N <: a \quad N <: N_1, \dots, N <: N_n \quad N_1, \dots, N_n \text{ ok}}{\text{for one } m \in \{1, \dots, n\} : a \doteq N_m}$		
Solution:			
SOLUTION $\frac{a \doteq G}{\sigma(a) = G}$	SOLUTION-GEN $\frac{a <: N}{a \doteq N \text{ or } a <: N}$	SOLUTION-REQUIREMENT $\frac{a <: N_1, \dots, a <: N_n}{\text{there must exist at least one : } a \doteq N}$	
Fail Conditions:			
FAIL-SUBTYPE $\frac{C < \dots > <: D < \dots > \quad C \text{ not extends } D}{\emptyset}$		FAIL-EQUALS $\frac{C < \dots > \doteq D < \dots > \quad C \neq D}{\emptyset}$	
Anti Circle Conditions:			
BUILD $\frac{a \doteq C < \dots, b, \dots >}{a \rightarrow b}$	CONNECT $\frac{a \rightarrow b \quad b \rightarrow c}{a \rightarrow c}$	FAIL-CIRCLE $\frac{a \rightarrow a}{\text{fail}}$	

Figure 5: Unify Algorithm Ω

Fail-Circle rules also disallow constraints like $a \doteq C < a >$, because the BUILD rule deduces a $a \rightarrow a$ which leads to *fail* by the FAIL-CIRCLE rule.

We need the SOLUTION-REQUIREMENT rule to force at least one type solution for every type placeholder in the input constraints (see example 4.1).

Example 4.1: SOLUTION-REQUIREMENT

$a \triangleleft \text{List}\langle x \rangle, a \triangleleft \text{List}\langle \text{String} \rangle$. We want our program to create a unifier for a which requires at least one constraint of the form $a \doteq \dots$. SOLUTION-REQUIREMENT forces the ASP solver to choose one of the following possibilities:

$$\begin{array}{c} a \triangleleft \text{List}\langle x \rangle, a \triangleleft \text{List}\langle \text{String} \rangle \\ \swarrow \quad \searrow \\ a \doteq \text{List}\langle x \rangle \quad a \doteq \text{List}\langle \text{String} \rangle \end{array}$$

In this case it does not matter which one gets chosen it will both lead to the same result. Let's take the $a \doteq \text{List}\langle x \rangle$ for example. Then we end up with a constraint $\text{List}\langle x \rangle \triangleleft \text{List}\langle \text{String} \rangle$ due to SUBST-L. ADAPT creates a $\text{List}\langle x \rangle \doteq \text{List}\langle \text{String} \rangle$ constraint and from there we get $x \doteq \text{String}$ by REDUCE. Together with $a \doteq \text{List}\langle x \rangle$ this leads to $a \doteq \text{List}\langle \text{String} \rangle$ (by SUBST-PARAM), which is a correct solution for the given constraints.

4.2. Differences to the Featherweight Generic Java Type Unification

The ASP unify algorithm Ω presented here is a toned down version of the algorithm presented in [2]. The main idea of our ASP prototype is to measure runtime performance especially in relation to Or-Constraints. When it comes to those core concepts the ASP algorithm has the same capabilities as the Type Inference algorithm for Generic Featherweight Java. Though unlike the original algorithm, we do not create Generic Type Variables. Instead, every type variable is directly assigned a concrete type. The prototype is not complete in the sense that it cannot find solutions that require polymorphic methods. However, it still finds all solutions that are possible without involving polymorphism.

The Unify algorithm presented in [2] and the prototype implemented in Scala figure out a solution by transforming the constraint set step by step. For example if a constraint $a \doteq \text{N}$ is found, all occurrences of a are replaced by N via substitution.

Our ASP implementation on the other hand does not use any state and therefore cannot change an existing constraint set. All possible substitutions are laid out by the grounding process. Afterwards all incorrect solutions are ruled out. This allows for a more declarative programming style, where we specify the type rules and let ASP figure out a solution for itself.

5. Proofs

An ASP solver tries to find the smallest possible set of constraints C_S , which satisfies all implication rules given in figure 5 while also containing the input constraints C . The constraint set C_S is called a stable model (see definition 2). We now want to prove two key properties of C_S : soundness and completeness. In our case, this means, that to prove soundness and completeness we have to show that C_S contains a $\sigma(a) = G$ for every type placeholder a used in the input constraints C and that this unifier σ is correct. Thereby showing that our algorithm computes only correct solutions (see Theorem 7 Soundness) and always finds a solution if there exists one (see Theorem 9 Completeness).

The first thing to show is that every type placeholder ends up in a constraint of the form $a \doteq G$ that is transformed into an unifier $\sigma(a) = G$ by the SOLUTION rule (G must not contain any type placeholders).

First, we prove that every type placeholder ends up in a constraint of the form $a \doteq N$. Then we show in lemma 6 that $a \doteq N \in C_S$ also means that $a \doteq G \in C_S$, which leads to lemma 5 (Closedness). Closedness means that every type placeholder ends up getting a unifier σ . Together with the substitution lemma 4, the soundness proof is apparent: Every constraint $S \triangleleft T \in C_S$ implies that $\sigma(S) \triangleleft \sigma(T) \in C_S$ and therefore σ must be a valid solution otherwise the algorithm will *fail* by one of the Fail-Rules at the bottom of figure 5.

Lemma 1 (Closedness). *Every type placeholder gets a unifier: If $a \in C$ and the input C ok then there either exists a stable model C_S with $\sigma(a) \in C_S$ or fail.*

Proof. Due to the Solution-Requirement and the S-Object rule we know that every type placeholder appears on the left side of a constraint of the form $a \doteq N$. With this two preliminaries and lemma 2 we know by lemma 6 that this also leads to a $a \doteq G$ constraint and therefore to $\sigma(a) = G$ through the Solution rule finishing the proof. \square

First we prove in lemma that any type placeholder a inside a given constraint set is getting at least the type `Object` assigned ($\sigma(a) = \text{Object}$). Afterwards we prove well-formedness for any solution (stable model) with the following lemma, which is needed for the Substitution lemma.

Lemma 2 (Stable Model is Well-Formed). *If C_S is a stable model for an input C with C ok then C_S ok*

Proof. We prove this by showing that no rule adds a not well-formed constraint. Assuming C ok then after applying one of the rules of Ω we get a C' with C' ok.

Case Subst-L intermediate, because no new type is created, only existing ones used in a new constraint.

Case Subst-R, Subst-Equal, Swap, Reduce, Solution-Gen, Solution-Requirement are intermediate as well for the same reason.

Case Subst-Param, Subst-Param-Left and Subst-Param-Right create a new type $C \langle P_1, \dots, G, \dots, P_n \rangle$, which is ok by WF-Type.

Case S-Object is correct, because a ok and `Object` ok by definition.

Case Reduce generates $P_i \doteq P'_i$ constraints. For each P_i and P'_i there are two possibilities: $P_i = a$ or $P_i = G$ and both times P_i ok by definition.

Case Adapt has the same reasoning as the Reduce case.

Case Super generates a constraint $a \doteq N_m$ where a ok by definition and N_m ok by premise of Super.

Case Solution-Gen and Solution-Requirement have the same reasoning as Super.

□

Lemma 3 is part of the substitution lemma 4:

Lemma 3 (Substitution-Step). *If C_S is a stable model containing C with C ok and $\{a \doteq G\} \in C_S$ then $[G/a]C \subseteq C_S$.*

Proof. We show this for every well-formed constraint in C :

1. $a \doteq G$: Subst-Equal implies $T \doteq G$ finishing the case, because $[T/a]G = G$
2. $S \doteq C\langle P_1, \dots, P_n \rangle$ and $a \notin S$: Each $P \in \{P_1, \dots, P_n\}$ is either a b or a type G' , which does not contain any type placeholders at all. If $b = a$ then we substitute by the Subst-Param rule. After applying Subst-Param consecutively to all parameters of $C\langle P_1, \dots, P_n \rangle$ we end up with $[G/a]S \doteq [G/a]C\langle P_1, \dots, P_n \rangle$
3. $N_1 \doteq N_2$: Apply Subst-Param to N_2 until we get $N_1 \doteq [G/a]N_2$. Then use Swap rule to get to step 2.
4. $N < S$: It is either a *fail* by the Fail-Subtype rule or we can apply Adapt and continue with step 1 - 3.
5. $a < S$: We apply the Subst-Param-Right rule similar to step 3.
6. $S < a$: Apply the Subst-Param-Left rule.

□

Lemma 4 (Substitution). *If C_S is a stable model and $(\{a \doteq G, \overline{a \doteq T}\} \cup C) \subseteq C_S$ and C_S ok then $[\overline{T/a}]C \in C_S$.*

Proof. By induction over $C' = \overline{a \doteq T}$.

Start $C' = \{a \doteq G\}$ implies $[G/a]C$ by lemma 3.

Step $C' = \{a \doteq G\} \cup \{\overline{a \doteq T}\}$. By lemma 3 we know that we also have $C'' = \{\overline{a \doteq [G/a]T}\}$, because $\{a \doteq T\}$ ok. There must be at least one $a' \doteq G' \in C''$, because C_S is a stable model and therefore does not contain a circle (see lemma 5). By 3 we get a $C''' = [([G'/a']\overline{T})/\overline{a}]C$ from $C'' \cup C$.

□

Lemma 5 (A Stable Model does not contain circles). *Let C_S be a stable model containing the constraints $a \doteq T$. If \overline{a} are all type placeholders contained in \overline{T} then the constraints $a \doteq T$ must house at least one $a \doteq G$.*

Proof. The proof is intermediate from the definition of circles 3 and the Fail-Circle rules. There must be either a circle or a $a \doteq G$ constraint if all type placeholders are involved, otherwise *fail* and C_S is not a stable model. □

The next lemma shows that the Solution-Requirement is enough to ensure a solution set. The algorithm Ω does not work if a circle is involved. It will *fail* otherwise. So there must exist at least one $a \doteq G$ constraint and substituting G for a leads to at least one other $b \doteq G$ constraint and so on. This ensures that a set of $a \doteq N$ in a stable model also means that $a \doteq G$ must also be inside this stable model.

Lemma 6. *If C_S is a stable model containing $\{a_1 \doteq N_1, \dots, a_n \doteq N_n\}$ then $\{a_1 \doteq G_1, \dots, a_n \doteq G_n\}$*

Proof. Proof by induction.

Start $\{a_1 \doteq N_1\}$ implies $a_1 \doteq G_1$, because every $b \in N_1$ leads to $b \doteq \text{Object}$ through S-Object and Solution-Gen, *Note:* $a \notin N_1$ if C_S is a stable model, due to the Fail-Circle rule.

Step $\{a_1 \doteq G, \overline{a \doteq N}\}$. By lemma 4 we know $[G/a_1]\overline{a \doteq N} \in C_S$. By lemma 5 there must be at least one $a \doteq G$ in $[G/a_1]\overline{a \doteq N}$, because $a_1 \cup \overline{a}$ are all type placeholders in C_S .

□

Theorem 7 (Soundness). *If C_S is a stable model containing C with C ok and containing a set of unifiers σ and no fail, then $\forall S \triangleleft T \in C : \sigma(S) \triangleleft \sigma(T)$ and $\forall S \doteq T \in C : \sigma(S) = \sigma(T)$.*

Proof. Additionally we know that for every type placeholder a there is a $\sigma(a) = G \in C_S$ by lemma 5. We prove it for each type of constraint individually:

\triangleleft **constraints:** By 4 we know that $\overline{\sigma(a)} = \overline{G}$ and C ok also implies $[\overline{G}/\overline{a}]C$.

\doteq **constraints** We have $[\overline{G}/\overline{a}]C$ by 4 and we know by lemma 5 that \overline{a} are all type placeholders contained in C . Therefore the only constraints remaining in $[\overline{G}/\overline{a}]C$ are the ones of the form $G_1 \doteq G_2$ (and $G_1 \triangleleft G_2$). The Fail-Equals and Reduce rules ensure that $G_1 \doteq G_2$ implies either $G_1 = G_2$ or *fail*.

□

The following Lemma 8 holds only in the absence of multiple inheritance. This restriction applies to Featherweight Java, which permits only single inheritance, unlike regular Java where a class may implement multiple interfaces. In our type system, the lemma is straightforward: due to single inheritance, each class has exactly one path upward through its supertypes.

Lemma 8. *$G \triangleleft G_1$ and $G \triangleleft G_2$ means $G_1 \triangleleft G_2$ or $G_2 \triangleleft G_1$ is correct*

Proof. Proof by induction over the subtype relations $G \triangleleft G_1$ (Relation 1) and $G \triangleleft G_1$ (Relation 2).

Case 1: S-Refl for Relation 1 $G = G_1$. Then $G_1 \triangleleft G_2$ by assumption.

Case 2: S-Refl for Relation 2 $G = G_2$. Analogous to Case 1:.

Case 3: S-Class for Relation 1 $G = C \triangleleft \overline{G}$ in $G \triangleleft G_1$ and `class C < \overline{X} > $\triangleleft N$` with $G_1 = [\overline{G}/\overline{X}]N$.

Subcase S-Refl for Relation 2 (see case Case 1:)

Subcase S-Class for Relation 2 means that $G_1 = G_2$, because there can only be one class definition for $C \langle \bar{X} \rangle$ with one supertype. $G_1 \prec G_2$ by S-Refl finishes the case.

Subcase S-Trans $G \prec G'$, $G' \prec G_2$. Here it must be $G_1 = G'$ and therefore $G_1 \prec G_2$ finishes the case.

This case has three subcases for each variant of Relation 2:

Case 4: S-Trans for Relation 1 $G \prec G'$, $G' \prec G_1$. This case has three subcases:

Subcase S-Refl for Relation 2 (see case Case 1:)

Subcase S-Class for Relation 2 (see case Case 3:)

Subcase S-Trans for Relation 2 $G \prec G''$, $G'' \prec G_2$. By i.h. we know from $G \prec G'$ and $G \prec G''$ that either $G' \prec G''$ or $G'' \prec G'$. Both variants are analogous and we will look at $G' \prec G''$. Then we have $G' \prec G_2$ by S-Trans. $G' \prec G_1$ and $G' \prec G_2$ lead to either $G_1 \prec G_2$ or $G_2 \prec G_1$ finishing the case.

□

Definition 3 (Circular Constraint). A set of constraints $\overline{a \doteq N}$ where $\forall N \in \bar{N} : fv(N) \neq \emptyset$ and \bar{a} contains all type placeholders used in \bar{N} ($\bar{a} = fv(\bar{N})$) is called a circle.

Theorem 9 ((partly) Completeness). The algorithm will find a solution if there exists one (with one exception: Circles).

Given a C and a σ ,

where C ok and $\forall S \prec T \in C : \sigma(S) \prec \sigma(T)$ and $\forall S \doteq T \in C : \sigma(S) = \sigma(T)$.

Then the algorithm will not fail, **except** when C contains a circle (see definition 3)

Proof. We show that none of the implication rules remove a possible solution.

Solution-Gen does nothing as long as there is at least one $a \doteq N$ constraint. The only time this happens is when there is no constraint like $a \doteq N$ or $N \prec a$ in the constraint set (Constraints of the form $N \prec a$ are turned to $a \doteq N$ by the Super rule). Consequently a only appears in a constraint set $C' \subseteq C$ with $C' = \overline{a \prec \bar{N}}$. By assumption we know that there is a $\sigma(a) = G$ with $\forall N \in \bar{N} : G \prec \sigma(N)$. By lemma 8 we know that there must exist one $\sigma(N)$ that is a subtype of all other $\sigma(N)$. Therefore setting $a \doteq N$ will not exclude any solution, as long as we choose the right N out of \bar{N} and our algorithm just tries every possibility, but must pick at least one induced by the Solution-Requirement rule.

Solution-Requirement This rule forces the Solution-Gen rule to create at least one $a \doteq N$ constraint (see Solution-Gen case).

Super We assume that all extends-Relations are well-formed (see rule WF-Class), which means that every supertype of a well-formed type N is well-formed as well. SUPER considers all possible supertypes, and therefore cannot miss a possible solution.

Reduce If $\sigma(\langle C, P_1, \dots, P_n \rangle) = \sigma(\langle C, P'_1, \dots, P'_n \rangle)$ then also $\sigma(P_1) = \sigma(P'_1), \dots, \sigma(P_n) = \sigma(P'_n)$.

Adapt Same as Reduce case.

Subst-Param and all other Subst-Cases. If $a \doteq G \in C$ then $\sigma(a) = G$, because σ is a valid solution. Knowing $\sigma(a) = G$ we can replace all occurrences of a by G without excluding any solution.

S-Object All classes in Java are a subtype of `Object`. $\sigma(a) \prec \text{Object}$ holds by definition of Java subtyping.

Swap Intermediate.

Solution Intermediate.

Fail-Subtype, Fail-Equals only exclude solutions, which are clearly wrong

Build, Connect, Fail-Circle only exclude circles (see Definition 3)

□

6. ASP Encoding

See appendix A for the complete program including an example input

ASP statements consist of a head and a body separated by an implication operator `:-`: `head :- body`. This statement is interpreted as an implication rule. If the premises in the body are satisfied the facts stated in the head are deduced. The implication rules defined in figure 5 are formulated in a way that can be translated to an ASP program. This chapter explains how to code our algorithm Ω in ASP. At first we give a ASP representation for each syntax element used in figure 3:

Syntax element	ASP representation
$\dots \prec \dots$	<code>subcons(. . . , . . .)</code>
$\dots \doteq \dots$	<code>equalcons(. . . , . . .)</code>
a	<code>tph("a")</code>
$C \langle \dots \rangle$	<code>type("C", params(. . .))</code>
<code>Object</code>	<code>type("Object", null)</code>

For further clarification we will present some examples:

$$\begin{aligned} C \langle \text{Object} \rangle &\implies \text{type}(\text{"C"}, \text{params}(\text{Object}, \text{null})) \\ a \prec b &\implies \text{subcons}(\text{tph}(\text{"a"}), \text{tph}(\text{"b"})) \\ \text{List} \langle a \rangle &\implies \text{type}(\text{"List"}, \text{params}(\text{tph}(\text{"a"}))) \end{aligned}$$

In addition to the constraint set C , our algorithm requires the class inheritance information of all classes that appear in the constraints. This information is essential for evaluating subtype relationships and is encoded in the form of ASP rules. Specifically, for every class declaration in the Java type system of the form `class C<X> extends D<X>` we generate a corresponding ASP rule:

Listing 1: Extends Relation as ASP rule

```
subtype(type("C", params(X)), type("D", params(X)))
:- subtype(type("C", params(X))).
```

These rules capture the inheritance hierarchy and serve as a static input to the algorithm, just like the constraint set C . Thus, the complete input to our algorithm consists of:

- The set of type constraints C
- The set of ASP rules encoding all relevant `extends` relations

This inheritance information is especially relevant for the `SUPER` and `ADAPT` rules, both of which contain premises of the form $N \triangleleft D \dots$. For example, when the input set contains a constraint like $a \triangleleft N$, the algorithm must determine the supertypes of N in order to apply the `SUPER` rule. This is exactly where the encoded inheritance rules come into play. The following example 6.1 illustrates this process in practice.

Example 6.1: Creating Supertypes

Assume two classes `Vector` and `List` are declared such that

```
class Vector<X> extends List<X>,
```

and let the constraint set be

$$C = \{ \text{Vector}\langle\text{String}\rangle \triangleleft a \}.$$

We need a helper rule in our ASP program that looks like this:

```
subtype(type(A, P)) :- subcons(type(A, P), _).
```

This deduces the fact:

```
subtype(type("Vector", params(type("String", null)))).
```

from the input constraint

```
subcons(type("Vector", params(type("String", null))),
tph("a")).
```

Now, the rule from Listing 1 generates the corresponding supertype:

```
subtype(type("Vector", params(type("String", null))),
type("List", params(type("String", null)))).
```

This reflects the subtyping relationship

$$\text{Vector}\langle\text{String}\rangle <: \text{List}\langle\text{String}\rangle.$$

With this information, the SUPER rule (see Listing 2) can select a valid supertype for a . In this case, it yields the ASP fact:

```
equalcons(tph("a"),
          type("List", params(type("String", null)))).
```

which corresponds to the constraint

$$a \dot{=} \text{List}\langle\text{String}\rangle.$$

Listing 2: Super-Rule

```
{equalcons(tph(A), type(D,DP)): subtype(type(C,CP), type(D,DP))}=1
:- subcons(type(C, CP), tph(A)).
```

The vital part is the generation of the Cartesian product of the Or-Constraints.
`subcons(A,B); orCons(C,D) :- orCons(subcons(A,B), subcons(C,D)).`
The operator ";" tells ASP to consider either the left or the right side. By supplying multiple Or-Constraints this way the ASP interpreter will consider all combinations, the Cartesian product of the Or-Constraints.

The rules implying a failure \emptyset are translated by leaving the head of the ASP statement empty. If the body of such rules is satisfied the algorithm considers the deduction as incorrect. See an example in listing 3 that shows an ASP encoding of the Fail-Equals rule.

Listing 3: Fail-Equals rule in ASP

```
:- equalcons(type(A, _), type(B, _)), A != B.
```

7. Benchmark

To evaluate the performance and practical applicability of our ASP implementation of the Unify algorithm for FGJ, we conducted two benchmarks:

1. **Massive Or-Constraints:** Tests Unify's ability to create and handle Cartesian products of big Or-Constraints.
2. **Matrix Example:** Typical benchmark used to test Java-TX type inference, where the Unify algorithm has to consider many possible variations of supertypes of the class `Matrix`.

Even though import statements in standard Java are purely syntactic and used only to avoid writing fully qualified class names, the current Java-TX implementation uses them to limit the search space for missing type annotations. The algorithm only considers "imported" types. This

makes Java-TX type inference unsuitable for typical Java development, where users expect to reuse classes without needing to import them in advance. In contrast, our ASP-based Unify algorithm aims to lift this restriction by considering the entire standard Java library as potential type candidates. To demonstrate this, we introduce the following benchmark program shown in Listing 5:

Listing 4: Benchmark

```
public class ThreeAdds {  
    void addTest(a, b, c, d){  
        a.add(b);  
        b.add(c);  
        c.add(d);  
        d.add(a);  
    }  
}
```

The `addTest` declaration in listing 5 is missing type annotations for its parameters `a`, `b`, `c`, `d`. We want our ASP implementation of the Unify algorithm to calculate all possible typings for the missing type annotations. Therefore we have to first generate a set of constraints representing the input problem. The method `addTest` has three calls `a.add(...)`, which leads to three large Or-Constraints. We use the Open-JDK standard library of the version 21, which contains nearly twenty thousand classes, including inner classes. They have a 200 different `add` methods all together. This leads to four Or-Constraints with 200 possibilities meaning a cartesian product with 1.6 billion elements. `clingo` finds a solution in under half a second.

Listing 5: Solution for Benchmark 5

```
public class ThreeAdds {  
    void addTest(javax.naming.directory.Attribute a,  
                java.util.concurrent.DelayQueue b,  
                java.beans.beancontext.BeanContextSupport c,  
                javax.naming.directory.BasicAttribute d){  
        a.add(b);  
        b.add(c);  
        c.add(d);  
        d.add(a);  
    }  
}
```

It is surprising how many possible type solutions the program in listing 5 has. Nearly every combination of types works in this case, because a lot of the `add` methods in the Java standard library take `Object` as an argument. One of the possible solutions is shown in listing 5 and should compile with the Open-JDK version 17. We assume that `clingo` spends most of the time during the grounding step and easily finds a possible solution, because finding one possible typing is easy after all possibilities are laid out.

The second benchmark is the `Matrix` example, which is also used by the Java-TX project to demonstrate functionality and serve as a stress test. The grayed-out types in the method

header ❶ are intended to be inferred by our type inference algorithm. As shown this example also utilizes the `var` keyword (introduced in Java 10 [10]). These missing types also have to be solved by our algorithm. Importantly, there are many valid solutions beyond just `Matrix mul(Matrix m)`, which makes this benchmark particularly interesting. The true complexity lies in the fact that super types of `Matrix` are also valid, and when wildcard types are taken into account, the number of possible solutions increases significantly. For example, `Vector<Vector<?extendsInteger>>` is a valid candidate for the parameter type `m`.

Our prototype implementation of the Unify algorithm does not currently support wildcard types, making a direct comparison to the original Java-TX implementation (written in Java) somewhat unfair. Anyhow, the Java implementation used by Java-TX typically requires several minutes to compute all possible solutions, whereas our ASP-based implementation achieves the same in just milliseconds.

Listing 6: Matrix Benchmark

```
class Matrix extends Vector<Vector<Integer>> {
❶ Matrix mul(Matrix m) {
    var ret = new Matrix();
    var i = 0;
    while(i < size()) {
        var v1 = this.elementAt(i);
        var v2 = new Vector<Integer>();
        var j = 0;
        while(j < v1.size()) {
            var erg = 0;
            var k = 0;
            while(k < v1.size()) {
                erg = erg + v1.elementAt(k)
                    * m.elementAt(k).elementAt(j);
                k++; }
            v2.addElement(new Integer(erg));
            j++; }
        ret.addElement(v2);
        i++; }
    return ret; } }
```

8. Outcome and Conclusion

ASP handles Or-Constraints surprisingly well. We tested our ASP implementation of the unification algorithm with the constraints originating from the program in figure 2. We compared it with the current implementation of the Unification algorithm in Java ⁴. We increased the complexity by adding more stacked method calls up to ten stacked calls and the interpreter `clingo` ⁵ was still able to handle it easily and finish computation in under 50 milliseconds. By

⁴<https://gitea.hb.dhbw-stuttgart.de/JavaTX/JavaCompilerCore>

⁵<https://potassco.org/clingo/>

contrast our Java implementation already takes multiple seconds processing time for the same input.

We are using this example for a fair comparison between the two implementations because it does not include generic type parameters causing the unification algorithm not to consider wildcard types. The Java implementation also supports Java wildcard types whereas the ASP implementation does not. It is unfortunately not possible to implement the unification algorithm including wildcard support with Answer Set Programming. The reason is that subtype checking in Java is Turing complete [11]. The grounding process of the ASP interpreter clingo would not terminate if the problem is turing complete [12]. The Java implementation is still able to spawn at least one solution in most cases and only never terminates for specific inputs, whereas the ASP program never terminates as soon as wildcards are involved.

9. Future Work

Using an ASP solver that does lazy grounding or no grounding at all [13] could be used to find solutions to unification problems with infinite search space. This would allow to extend the type system to wildcards as in [1].

The ASP version of our global type inference algorithm is not complete yet. It does not support constraints of the form $a \leq C\langle a \rangle$. Those constraints can appear in environments with F-Bounded generics like `String extends Comparable<String>` and `Box<A extends Comparable<A>>`.

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A. ASP Program + Example Input

```
% TEST INPUT

% Extends-Relations
subtype(type("java.lang.Boolean", null), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subtype(type("java.lang.Boolean", null)).
subtype(type("java.lang.Integer", null), type("java.lang.Number", null)) :- subtype(type("java.lang.Integer", null)).
subtype(type("java.lang.Number", null), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subtype(type("java.lang.Number", null)).

% java.util.Vector<X> extends List<X>
subtype(type("java.util.Vector", params(XX)), type("java.util.List", params(XX))) :- subtype(type("java.util.Vector", params(XX))).
% Matrix extends List<List<Integer>>
subtype(type("Matrix", null), type("java.util.List", params(type("java.util.List", params(type("java.lang.Integer", null)))))) :-
  subtype(type("Matrix", null)).
% MyPair<X, Y> extends Pair<X, X>
subtype(type("MyPair", params(XX, XY)), type("Pair", params(XX, XX))) :- subtype(type("MyPair", params(XX, XY))).
% Pair extends Object
subtype(type("Pair", params(XX, XY)), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subtype(type("Pair", params(XX, XY))).
% List extends Object
subtype(type("List", params(XX)), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subtype(type("List", params(XX))).

% Constraints:

% Or-Constraint: {List<Integer> <. a | List<Boolean> <. a}
orCons(
  undCons(
    subcons(type("java.util.List", params(type("java.lang.Integer", null))), type("java.util.List", params(tph("a"))))
    , null
    , orCons(
      undCons(
        subcons(type("java.util.List", params(type("java.lang.Boolean", null))), type("java.util.List", params(tph("a"))))
        , null
      )
    )
  ).
% Constraints: List<a> <. b, m <. b, m <. Matrix
subcons(type("java.util.List", params(tph("a"))), tph("b")).
subcons(tph("m"), type("java.util.List", params(tph("b")))).
subcons(tph("m"), type("Matrix", null)).

% START OF THE ALGORITHM:

% Everything is a subtype of "Object"
subtype(A, type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subtype(A).

% Or-Constraints
undCons(A, B) :- orCons(undCons(A, B), null).
undCons(A, B) ; orCons(C, D) :- orCons(undCons(A, B), orCons(C, D)).

% undCons
subcons(A, B) :- undCons(subcons(A, B), _).
undCons(C, D) :- undCons(_, undCons(C, D)).
equalCons(A, B) :- undCons(equalCons(A, B), _).
undCons(B, C) :- undCons(A, undCons(B, C)).

% Subtyping
subtype(A, A) :- subtype(A). % reflexive
subtype(A, A) :- subtype(A, B). % reflexive
subtype(B) :- subtype(A, B). % transitive
subtype(A, C) :- subtype(A, B), subtype(B, C). % transitive
% named Subtyping
namedSubtype(A, B) :- subtype(type(A, AP), type(B, BP)).
% is reflexive and transitive because subtype it stems from subtype

% generate the subtype relations for every constraint where one is needed: (this could be optimized)
subtype(type(A, P)) :- subcons(_, type(A, P)).
subtype(type(A, P)) :- subcons(type(A, P), _).

% subst:
subst(tph(A), type(N, P)) :- sigma(tph(A), type(N, P)).

% subst-L:
subcons(B, C) :- subst(A, B), subcons(A, C).
% subst-R:
subcons(C, B) :- subst(A, B), subcons(C, A).
% subst-Equal:
equalCons(B, C) :- subst(A, B), equalCons(A, C).

% swap:
equalCons(A, B) :- equalCons(B, A).

%S-Object
```

```

subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(tph(A), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(_, tph(A)).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A)))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _, _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _, _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _, _, _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(type(_, params(tph(A))), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- subcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(tph(A), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(_, tph(A)).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A)))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _, _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _, _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(_, type(_, params(tph(A), _, _, _))).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(type(_, params(tph(A))), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).
subcons(tph(A), type("java.lang.Object", null)) :- equalcons(type(_, params(tph(A), _, _)), _).

% Subst-Param using a maxdepth:
maxdepth(5).
depth(T2) :- subst(T, T2).
depth(type(A, null), 0) :- depth(type(A, null)).
depth(T) :- depth(type(A, params(T))).
depth(T) :- depth(type(A, params(T, T1))).
depth(T1) :- depth(type(A, params(T, T1))).
depth(T) :- depth(type(A, params(T, T1, T2))).
depth(T1) :- depth(type(A, params(T, T1, T2))).
depth(T2) :- depth(type(A, params(T, T1, T2))).
depth(type(A, params(T)), D+1) :- depth(type(A, params(T))), depth(T, D).
depth(type(A, params(T, T1)), D+D1+1) :- depth(type(A, params(T, T1))), depth(T, D), depth(T1, D1).
depth(type(A, params(T, T1, T2)), D+D1+D2+1) :- depth(type(A, params(T, T1, T2))), depth(T, D), depth(T1, D1), depth(T2, D2).
% calculate depth before substitution
depth(T2) :- subst(_, T2).

% Subst-Param:
equalcons(A, type(C, params(T2))) :- equalcons(A, type(C, params(T))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
equalcons(A, type(C, params(T2, P2))) :- equalcons(A, type(C, params(T, P2))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
equalcons(A, type(C, params(P1, T2))) :- equalcons(A, type(C, params(P1, T))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
equalcons(A, type(C, params(T2, P2, P3))) :- equalcons(A, type(C, params(T, P2, P3))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
equalcons(A, type(C, params(P1, T2, P3))) :- equalcons(A, type(C, params(P1, T, P3))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
equalcons(A, type(C, params(P1, P2, T2))) :- equalcons(A, type(C, params(P1, P2, T))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.

% Subst-Param-Right:
subcons(A, type(C, params(T2))) :- subcons(A, type(C, params(T))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
subcons(A, type(C, params(T2, P2))) :- subcons(A, type(C, params(T, P2))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
subcons(A, type(C, params(P1, T2))) :- subcons(A, type(C, params(P1, T))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
subcons(A, type(C, params(T2, P2, P3))) :- subcons(A, type(C, params(T, P2, P3))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
subcons(A, type(C, params(P1, T2, P3))) :- subcons(A, type(C, params(P1, T, P3))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.
subcons(A, type(C, params(P1, P2, T2))) :- subcons(A, type(C, params(P1, P2, T))), subst(T, T2), depth(T2, D), maxdepth(Dmax), D < Dmax.

% adapt
equalcons(type(D,P3), type(D,P2)) :- subcons(type(C,P), type(D, P2)), subtype(type(C, P), type(D, P3)).

% reduce
equalcons(P1, PP1) :- equalcons(type(C, params(P1)), type(C, params(PP1))).
equalcons(P1, PP1) :- equalcons(type(C, params(P1, P2)), type(C, params(PP1, PP2))).
equalcons(P2, PP2) :- equalcons(type(C, params(P1, P2)), type(C, params(PP1, PP2))).
equalcons(P1, PP1) :- equalcons(type(C, params(P1, P2, P3)), type(C, params(PP1, PP2, PP3))).
equalcons(P2, PP2) :- equalcons(type(C, params(P1, P2, P3)), type(C, params(PP1, PP2, PP3))).
equalcons(P3, PP3) :- equalcons(type(C, params(P1, P2, P3)), type(C, params(PP1, PP2, PP3))).

```

```

% super
{ equalcons(tph(A), type(D, DP)): subtype(type(C, CP), type(D, DP)) } == 1 :- subcons(type(C, CP), tph(A)).

% Solution-Gen
{ equalcons(tph(A), type(T,P)) } :- subcons(tph(A), type(T,P)).

% Solution-Requirement
:- subcons(tph(A), _), not sigma(tph(A), _).

%Solution:
tphs( P ) :- equalcons(tph(A), type(C, P)).
sigma(tph(A), type(C,P)) :- equalcons(tph(A), type(C, P)), not tphs(_, P).

% fail-equals
:- equalcons(type(C, CP), type(D, DP)), C != D.

% fail-subtype
:- subcons(type(C, CP), type(D, DP)), not namedSubtype(C, D).

% Build
connected(A,B) :- equalcons(tph(A), type(_,params(tph(B))))).
connected(A,B) :- equalcons(tph(A), type(_,params(tph(B),_))).
connected(A,B) :- equalcons(tph(A), type(_,params(_,tph(B))))).
connected(A,B) :- equalcons(tph(A), type(_,params(tph(B),_,_))).
connected(A,B) :- equalcons(tph(A), type(_,params(_,tph(B),_))).
connected(A,B) :- equalcons(tph(A), type(_,params(_,_,tph(B))))).
%connect
connected(A,C) :- connected(A,B), connected(A,C).
%Fail-circle
:- connected(A,A).

%% Helpers
%tphs:
tphs(tph(P), params(tph(P))) :- tphs( params(tph(P))).
tphs(P) :- tphs( params(type(C, P))).
tphs(tph(A), params(type(C, P))) :- tphs( params(type(C, P))), tphs(tph(A), P).

tphs(tph(P), params(X, tph(P))) :- tphs( params(X, tph(P))).
tphs(tph(P), params(tph(P), X)) :- tphs( params(tph(P), X)).
tphs(P) :- tphs( params(X, type(C, P))).
tphs(P) :- tphs( params(type(C, P), X)).
tphs(tph(A), params(X, type(C, P))) :- tphs( params(X, type(C, P))), tphs(tph(A), P).
tphs(tph(A), params(type(C, P), X)) :- tphs( params(type(C, P), X)), tphs(tph(A), P).

tphs(tph(P), params(tph(P), X, Y)) :- tphs( params(tph(P), X, Y)).
tphs(tph(P), params(X, tph(P), Y)) :- tphs( params(X, tph(P), Y)).
tphs(tph(P), params(X,Y,tph(P))) :- tphs( params(X, Y, tph(P))).
tphs(P) :- tphs( params(type(C, P), X, Y)).
tphs(P) :- tphs( params(X, type(C, P),Y)).
tphs(P) :- tphs( params(X,Y,type(C, P))).
tphs(tph(A), params(type(C, P), X, Y)) :- tphs( params(type(C, P), X, Y)), tphs(tph(A), P).
tphs(tph(A), params(X, type(C, P), Y)) :- tphs( params(X, type(C, P), Y)), tphs(tph(A), P).
tphs(tph(A), params(X, Y, type(C, P))) :- tphs( params(X, Y, type(C, P))), tphs(tph(A), P).

% Only print unifiers
#show sigma/2.

```